

Sequential choice and self-reinforcing rankings

Pantelis P. Analytis, Francesco Cerigioni, Alexandros Gelastopoulos and Hrvoje Stojic

University of Southern Denmark, Universitat Pompeu Fabra and Barcelona School of Economics

Introduction

In many settings people use the behavior of others as a source of information that can influence their own behavior. This problem, commonly referred to as social learning, has been extensively studied in the social sciences and understandably so—social learning is crucial for understanding how information is aggregated and for predicting social outcomes and welfare (Banerjee, 1992; Ellison & Fudenberg, 1993; Smith & Sørensen, 2000; Golub & Jackson, 2012; Che & Hörner, 2018). A possible concern with this literature is the plethora of available models that many times reach very different conclusions about the possible limiting behavior. This concern becomes pressing when we think about the new economy and the dependence of many major websites on the sequential aggregation of information from a population of agents, especially in the form of rankings.

Online marketplaces, social media, and search engines rank content for their users and their algorithms rely on implicit or explicit user feedback, such as clicks, sales and likes to update and re-rank their content (i.e. products, webpages, etc.). There is plenty of evidence to suggest that people are more likely to choose or interact with items that appear higher on the list (Joachims, Granka, Pan, Hembrooke, & Gay, 2005; Salganik, Dodds, & Watts, 2006; Caplin, Dean, & Martin, 2011). Similar phenomena are encountered in offline settings where rankings convey socially aggregated information and influence people's choices, as in the cases of journal or department rankings (Laband, 2013; Espeland & Sauder, 2007). Ideally, we would like to reach a ranking that reflects the quality of the options available. It is not obvious though, whether aggregating feedback sequentially can lead to a ranking that is optimal, in the sense that options that are valuable to more people are ranked first.

In studying the dynamics of rankings that aggregate information from people's choices, one has to make assumptions about people's choice behavior, in particular how it is affected by the ranking. If different behavioral assumptions lead to very different limiting behaviors, as it seems to be the case in the social learning literature (Mobius & Rosenblat, 2014), any results would be relevant only in the limited contexts where these behavioural assumptions hold true (or approximately true). Since it is rarely possible to pin down entirely the way people behave when making choices, such dependence on specific assumptions can potentially be fatal for the usefulness of these results in predicting the long-term dynamics of rankings.

In this paper we show that, at least in some cases, it is possible to avoid this conclusion. We propose a general framework which addresses the complex dynamic nature of the problem discussed above and gives precise predictions for the limiting structure. Our main assumption is that the information available about other people's choices is in the form of a *popularity ranking*, i.e. which option is currently the most popular one, which one is second and so on. In this setting, we find quite general conditions under which the ranking converges and, moreover, we characterize the possible limit rankings in terms of the choice probabilities. The assumption we impose on the choice behavior of the agents is a weak form of preference for highly ranked options. Surprisingly, this assumption is satisfied by several prominent behavioural models like satisficing (Simon, 1955; Caplin et al., 2011), consideration set models (Manzini & Mariotti, 2014), drift-diffusion models (Fudenberg, Strack, & Strzalecki, 2018), models of position-dependent attention (Germano, Gómez, & Le Mens, 2019), but also by social learning models building on discrete choice theory (Brock & Durlauf, 2001) and even Banerjee's herding model (1992) in which agents are fully rational. This means that the framework we propose can be applied to get sharp

predictions about the dynamics of popularity rankings under a variety of different behavioral assumptions.

Let us give some details about how this generality is achieved. Consider a set of items X , the collection χ of all subsets of X and the set \mathcal{R} of all possible rankings (orderings) of the items in X . A *ranking-based choice function* is a map $\pi: \chi \times \mathcal{R} \rightarrow [0,1]$, such that $\sum_{A \in \chi} \pi(A, r) = 1$ for each $r \in \mathcal{R}$. The quantity $\pi(A, r)$ is interpreted as the probability of choosing exactly the items in the set A when the items are ranked according to $r \in \mathcal{R}$. Thus, our choice model is similar to a choice from lists model (Rubinstein & Salant, 2006), except that a ranking must contain all elements of X , and the choice is stochastic. Also, the decision maker is allowed to choose a set of items from X , rather than a single item. The probability that $a \in X$ is included in the set of items chosen, when the ranking is r , is denoted by $q(a, r) = \sum_{A \ni a} \pi(A, r)$.

Our main assumption for π is a ranking-based reinforcement assumption: items that are ranked higher are generally more likely to be chosen. However, this condition may interact with the desirability of the different items. Specifically, we allow for an asymmetric relation P on X , with aPb roughly interpreted as a being preferred to b by the average agent. This relation doesn't have to be transitive nor complete¹, and it might as well be the empty relation. Our reinforcement assumption is roughly saying that if a is more highly ranked than b in the ranking r and bPa (i.e. b is not more desirable than a), then $q(a, r) > q(b, r)$. No assumption is made if aPa . In terms of a search engine, for example, this would mean that if result a is both at least as relevant as result b (i.e. aPa) and it appears higher, then it should be more likely for a to be chosen. It turns out that this assumption is weak enough to be satisfied by a variety of models in the literature.

Next we consider a large number of agents that choose sequentially from the set X , according to the choice function π . Agent $n \in N$ observes the popularity ranking R_{n-1} , that is the ranking of the items in X by number of choices among the first

$n-1$ agents. This would be the case, for example, if an online marketplace displayed the various items in a category ranked by numbers of sales, since each user would see them ranked by popularity in terms of purchases by previous agents. We thus assume that the choice probabilities for the n -th agent are given by $\pi(\cdot, R_{n-1})$. With this sequential choice structure, and under the reinforcement assumption for π (see previous paragraph), we show that as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the popularity ranking R_n converges to some constant ranking with probability 1. However, there are in principle multiple possible limits. We characterize these possible limits in terms of the map π . If we know the limit ranking, we can also find the market shares of the various items, that is the proportion of agents that choose each of the items, again in terms of the map π . Each item may also carry a utility for an agent that chooses it. We are interested in the average utility experienced by a large number of agents. We show that this average utility converges, with its limit being a function of the limit ranking. This implies in particular that we can compare the various rankings in terms of the average utility that they result in. The fact that there are generally multiple possible limit rankings implies that we may end up at a sub-optimal limit ranking in terms of average utility.

Importantly, the utility function may be intertwined with the ranking; on one hand, agents might gain utility by choosing popular items, so we allow the utility to depend on the ranking. On the other hand, the utility might affect the choice probabilities, as is the case for example for rational, utility-maximizing agents. We model the dependence of the choice probabilities on the utility by adding structure to the choice function, now written as $\pi(A, r, w)$, where w is the agent type and may carry information about the utility function of the agent. It turns out that all our results continue to hold as long as agent types are chosen i.i.d. from a given distribution. In the full paper we (i) introduce our framework and assumptions, (ii) treat the important case of two items, which is simpler and intuitive, but already contains many of the ideas involved in the general case, (iii) present the theoretical results for the general

¹ We adopt the economics convention and call *complete* a relation satisfying that for any $a \neq b$, either

aPb or bPa . In mathematics such connections are called *connected*.

case, i.e. for any finite number of items (iv) show how several important behavioral models from the literature satisfy our assumptions, and (v) describe some alternative interpretations of our framework.

References

- Banerjee, A. V. (1992). A simple model of herd behavior. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 107 (3), 797–817.
- Brock, W. A., & Durlauf, S. N. (2001). Discrete choice with social interactions. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 68 (2), 235–260.
- Caplin, A., Dean, M., & Martin, D. (2011). Search and satisficing. *American Economic Review*, 101 (7), 2899–2922.
- Che, Y.-K., & Hörner, J. (2018). Recommender systems as mechanisms for social learning. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 133 (2), 871–925.
- Ellison, G., & Fudenberg, D. (1993). Rules of thumb for social learning. *Journal of Political Economy*, 101 (4), 612–643.
- Espeland, W. N., & Sauder, M. (2007). Rankings and reactivity: How public measures recreate social worlds. *American Journal of Sociology*, 113 (1), 1–40.
- Fudenberg, D., Strack, P., & Strzalecki, T. (2018). Speed, accuracy, and the optimal timing of choices. *American Economic Review*, 108 (12), 3651–84.
- Germano, F., Gómez, V., & Le Mens, G. (2019). The few-get-richer: a surprising consequence of popularity-based rankings? In *Proceedings of the world wide web conference* (pp. 2764–2770).
- Golub, B., & Jackson, M. O. (2012). How homophily affects the speed of learning and best-response dynamics. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 127 (3), 1287–1338.
- Joachims, T., Granka, L. A., Pan, B., Hembrooke, H., & Gay, G. (2005). Accurately interpreting clickthrough data as implicit feedback. In *Proceedings of the 28th international acm sigir conference on research and development in information retrieval* (Vol. 5, pp. 154–161).
- Laband, D. N. (2013). On the use and abuse of economics journal rankings. *The Economic Journal*, 123 (570), F223–F254.
- Manzini, P., & Mariotti, M. (2014). Stochastic choice and consideration sets. *Econometrica*, 82 (3), 1153–1176.
- Mobius, M., & Rosenblat, T. (2014). Social learning in economics. *Annual Review of Economics*, 6 (1), 827–847.
- Rubinstein, A., & Salant, Y. (2006). A model of choice from lists. *Theoretical Economics*, 1 (1), 3–17.
- Salganik, M. J., Dodds, P. S., & Watts, D. J. (2006). Experimental study of inequality and unpredictability in an artificial cultural market. *Science*, 311 (5762), 854–856.
- Simon, H. A. (1955). A behavioral model of rational choice. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 69 (1), 99–118.
- Smith, L., & Sørensen, P. (2000). Pathological outcomes of observational learning. *Econometrica*, 68 (2), 371–398.